

Synthesis and Physiological Activity of Thiazolidinyl-benzoxazines

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Some 7-(2-aryl-4-oxo-3-thiazolidinyl)-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazine-3-ones (5) were prepared by addition, condensation of mercaptoacetic acid to arylidene-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazine-3-one (4). Compounds 4 and 5 were compared with Dithane M-45 for their antifungal activity against *Helminthosporium oryzae* and *Cephalosporium sacchari*, and correlated with structural features

THIAZOLIDINONES were found to exhibit wide spectrum pharmacological activities. Thiazolidinones possess antitubercular, anaesthetic, antifungal and hypnotic activity¹⁻⁴. Some of the 2H-1,4-benzoxazines have attracted attention as antispasmodics⁵. These reports prompted us to synthesise the title compounds as potential antifungal agents.

7-Nitro-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazine-3-one (2), a key intermediate compound, was prepared⁶ by nitration of 3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazine-3-one (1) and its corresponding 7-amino compound following the reported procedure⁷.

7-Amino-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazine-3-one (3) on condensation with substituted aromatic aldehydes resulted in Schiff bases (4). 7-Arylidene-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazine-3-ones (4) on cyclocondensation with mercaptoacetic acid in dry benzene yielded 7-(2-aryl-4-oxo-3-thiazolidinyl)-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazine-3-ones (5) (Scheme 1). The products 4 and 5 have been characterised by analytical and spectral (ir, pmr) data. A signal at δ 8.35 in pmr spectrum was characteristic of azomethine (4) proton and a sharp band at 1625 cm^{-1} in ir spectrum was characteristic of C=N stretching. I.r. spectrum of 5 showed absorptions at 1645 (lactam C=O) and 1690 cm^{-1} (tertiary amide C=O).

Melting points were determined in open capillaries. Ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer, and pmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 instrument using TMS as internal standard.

Experimental

Arylidene-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazine-3-one (4): A mixture of 7-amino-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazine-3-one (3) (1.65 g, 0.01 mol) and aryl aldehyde (1 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed in 96% ethanol (16 ml) for 4 h in the presence of two drops of piperidine. The contents were concentrated and cooled to give Schiff bases (4) in 90% yield and recrystallised from 96% ethanol; 4a ν_{max} 1680 (C=O), 1625 (C=N) and 3200 (NH) cm^{-1} ; $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 4.54 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.41 (1H, d, J 7Hz, C₈-H), 7.74 (2H, m, C₆-C₈-H) and 8.34 (1H, s, azomethine proton).

- a, R = H, R' = H
- b, R = CH₃, R' = H
- c, R = Cl, R' = H
- d, R = NO₂, R' = H
- e, R = OCH₃, R' = H
- f, R = Cl, R' = Cl
- g, R = OCH₃, R' = OH

Scheme 1 Reagents: (i) EtOH, 2 drops piperidine; (ii) HS-CH₂-COOH/dry C₆H₆.

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7-(2-Aryl-4-oxo-3-thiazolidinyl)-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazine-3-ones (5): Mercaptoacetic acid (0.015 mol) was added to a well stirred solution of Schiff bases (4) (0.01 mol) in dry benzene and refluxed for 20 h using Dean and Stark trap. Solvent was removed by vacuum distillation and the residue treated with 1% NaHCO₃ solution, extracted with ether, dried with Na₂SO₄ and ether distilled off to give thiazolidinones (5) in 80% yield and recrystal-

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF SCHIFF BASES AND THIAZOLIDINYLBENZOXAZINES*

Compd. no.	R	R'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
4a	H	H	176	90	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂	70.96 (71.42)	4.39 (4.76)	10.88 (11.10)
b	CH ₃	H	196	75	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂	72.33 (72.18)	5.07 (5.26)	10.48 (10.52)
c	Cl	H	179	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₂	62.69 (62.82)	3.84 (3.83)	9.80 (9.77)
d	NO ₂	H	209	80	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃	60.12 (60.60)	3.52 (3.70)	14.16 (14.14)
e	OCH ₃	H	260	80	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃	68.49 (68.08)	4.44 (4.96)	9.93 (9.92)
f	Cl	Cl	222	65	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	54.80 (56.07)	3.19 (3.11)	8.74 (8.72)
g	OCH ₃	OH	168	60	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃	64.91 (64.42)	4.41 (4.69)	9.33 (9.30)
5a	H	H	142	85	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ SO ₂	62.05 (62.57)	4.03 (4.29)	8.54 (8.58)
b	CH ₃	H	270	55	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ SO ₂	63.64 (63.52)	4.36 (4.70)	8.20 (8.23)
c	Cl	H	265	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ SO ₂	56.92 (56.58)	3.32 (3.60)	7.76 (7.76)
d	NO ₂	H	273	45	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ SO ₃	54.17 (54.98)	3.49 (3.50)	11.26 (11.32)
e	OCH ₃	H	205	48	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ SO ₃	59.66 (60.67)	4.40 (4.49)	7.81 (7.86)
f	Cl	Cl	234	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₂ SO ₂	51.59 (51.64)	2.96 (3.03)	7.04 (7.08)
g	OCH ₃	OH	282	50	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ SO ₃	63.66 (63.52)	4.91 (4.70)	8.20 (8.23)

*All compounds crystallised from ethanol.

TABLE 2—ANTIFUNGAL SCREENING DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4 AND 5

Average percent inhibition after 96 h.

Compd. no.	R	R'	<i>C. oryzae</i>			<i>C. sacchari</i>		
			1 000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm	1 000 ppm	100 ppm	10 ppm
4a	H	H	48	29	16	51	26	14
b	CH ₃	H	36	27	12	45	19	9
c	NO ₂	H	39	21	10	36	17	8
d	Cl	H	58	31	20	70	38	30
e	OCH ₃	H	64	37	26	65	31	19
f	OCH ₃	OH	67	37	22	64	29	17
g	Cl	Cl	71	33	28	75	40	30
5a	H	H	42	20	8	53	34	17
b	CH ₃	H	35	18	6	33	19	8
c	NO ₂	H	43	26	11	40	23	13
d	Cl	H	60	33	19	55	29	20
e	OCH ₃	H	58	28	14	58	39	17
f	OCH ₃	OH	61	32	15	60	37	22
g	Cl	Cl	66	31	16	63	40	28
Dithane M-45			100	89	72	100	90	74

lised from 96% ethanol; 5a ν_{max} 3 230 (NH), 1 645 (lactam C=O) and 1 965 cm⁻¹ (tertiary amide C=O); δ (DMSO-d₆) 8.63 (1H, s, tertiary proton), 10.75 (1H, bs, NH), 7.5-7.9 (8H, m, Ar-H) and 4.45-4.59 (4H, d, J 12Hz, oxazine and thiazolidinone methylene protons).

The physical data of compounds 4 and 5 are given in Table 1.

Antifungal screening: The antifungal activity of the compounds 4 and 5 was evaluated against *H. oryzae* and *C. sacchari* by usual agar-plate technique* at 1 000, 100 and 10 ppm concentrations. A commercial fungicide Dithane M-15 was also tested under similar conditions for comparing the results (Table 2).

All the tested compounds of 4 and 5 were toxic to both the test fungi at 1 000 ppm and not so spectacular at lower concentrations, 100 ppm and 10 ppm. In general, compounds 4 were more potent than thiazolidinyl benzoxazines (5). Compounds having halogens or methoxyl group were found to show higher antifungal activity over those having hydrogen or methyl group.

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